

Nanochannels Preparation and Application in Biosensing

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ABSTRACT

Selective transport in nanochannels (protein-based ion channels) is already used in living systems for electrical signaling in nerves and muscles and this natural behavior is being approached for the application of biomimetic nanochannels in biosensors. Based on this principle single nanochannels and nanochannels arrays seem to bring new advantages for biosensor development and applications. The purpose of this review is to provide a general comprehensive and critical overview on the latest trends in the development of nanochannels based biosensing systems. A detailed description and discussion of representative and recent works covering the main nanochannels fabrication techniques, the nanoporous materials characterizations and specially their application in both electrochemical and optical sensing systems is given. The state of the art of the developed technology may open the way to new advances in the integration of nanochannels with (bio)molecules and synthetic receptors for the development of novel biodetection systems that can be extended to many other applications with interest for clinical analysis, safety and security as well as environmental and other industrial studies and applications

KEYWORDS

Nanochannels, nanopores, biosensing, protein sensing, DNA sensing, stochastic sensing, solid-state ion channel, optical sensing, electrochemical sensing.

The development and application of biosensing systems is one of the leading sectors of state-of-the-art nanoscience and nanotechnology. Biosensing systems are under commercial development for numerous applications, that include the detection of pathogens, the measurement of clinical parameters, the monitoring of environmental pollutants and other industrial and sensing and security uses. The most effective way of providing biosensing systems to potential customers, especially those with limited budgets, might be to modify the technology so that it can run on everyday equipment, rather than on specialized apparatuses.^{1,2} In this context, the use of nanomaterials is showing to be advantageous not only in the design of bioanalytical systems but also in the improvement of existing biodetection systems.³⁻⁷

Nowadays, there is an increasing interest in measuring and investigating transport and electrochemical phenomena in membrane samples that contain a single pore of nanoscopic diameter. Selective transport in nanochannels (protein-based ion channels) is used in living systems for electrical signalling in nerves and muscles. This natural behaviour is being approached for the application of nanochannels in biosensors. Nanoporous materials also show a dramatic increase in surface/volume ratio that enhances the signals corresponding to interaction between solutes and surfaces including biomolecule reactions. Based on this principle nanochannels arrays and single nanochannels seem to present promising new features for biosensor development.

The fundament of sensing using nanochannels is based on the concept of the Coulter counter, a device patented in 1953 by Wallace Coulter^{8,9} that consists in two chambers containing an electrolyte solution and separated by one or few more microchannels. When a microscopic particle enters through the microchannel, a change in the electrical conductance is detected. This resistance change can be recorded as electric current or voltage pulse, which can be correlated to size, mobility, surface charge and concentration of the particles. Due to its simplicity, this device has been used in hospitals for the determination of white and red blood cells and also in the industry of paint, glass,

ceramics and food manufacture. The Coulter counter was designed to measure particles in the micrometric scale, but for biosensing purposes devices able to detect molecules in the nanometric scale are needed and for this reason the research in this field is focused in the last years on the development of channels of nanometric size¹⁰⁻¹² inspired in the natural ion channels and able to detect molecules such as proteins, DNA strands, *etc.* (Figure 1A).

Along this review the terms “nanopore” and “nanochannel” will be found since at present they are in common mutual use, so it is important to clarify first the differences between both structures. In terms of shape and dimensions, “nanopore” is defined as a pore having a diameter of 1 to 100 nm and being this diameter larger than its depth. When the pore depth is much larger than the diameter, the structure is generally called “nanochannel”. Due to that, nanochannels present a better selectivity on the transported molecules compared to the nanopores.¹³

Some recent reviews have described in detail the strategies for the integration of nanochannels, from ion channels to the fully synthetic nanochannels.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Insertion/integration of biological/natural ion channels into lipid bilayers, forming a biological ion channel represents the pioneer strategy. The performance of this outstanding sensing system has been even improved by building of solid-state/artificial nanochannels embedded in chemically and mechanically robust synthetic membranes, using various materials and technologies. These strategies will be discussed in detail in the following sections, giving a critical view of the main advantages and drawbacks of each one and focusing always on the objective to be used in biosensing applications.

BIOLOGICAL ION CHANNELS

Nature structures have inspired laboratory research for many years. Bioinspired materials have attracted great interest because of their unique properties which have given rise to many applications.^{17,18} For example, ion channels play important roles in living organisms maintaining normal physiological conditions, responding directly to molecules or to some physical stimuli and serving as “smart” gates to ensure selective ion transport. They exhibit also selective ion conduction and the ability to gate-open in response to an appropriate stimulus. Furthermore, in these natural ion

channels the ionic current flows through and this current is altered when a molecule binds to a specific region of the channel.¹⁹ All these fundamentals are being approached for biosensing purposes, by using biological biomimetic nanochannels, simulating this natural behaviour.^{20,21}

Protein channels

The protein ion channels used for the first time in real experimental approaches for sensing were the K⁺-selective ion channel,²² the channel formed by *Staphylococcus aureus* α -hemolysin²³ and the channel formed by *Bacillus anthracis* protective antigen²⁴ (Figure 1B). Between them, the most widely used for biosensing is the α -hemolysin bacterial protein pore that consists on a structure formed by self-assembly of seven identical polypeptides from *Staphylococcus aureus*²⁵ (Figure 1C). The mushroom-shaped heptameric α -hemolysin pore consists of a 14- stranded transmembrane β -barrel (a large beta-sheet that twists and coils to form a closed structure in which the first strand is hydrogen bonded to the last) and a bigger cap region which is positioned outside the membrane.²⁶ The external dimensions of the pore are 10 x 10 nm, and the inner diameter of the central channel varies between 2.9 nm at the cis entrance, 4.1 nm in the internal cavity, 1.3 nm at the inner constriction, and 2 nm at the trans entrance of the β -barrel (Figure 1C). The detection of analytes through nanochannel blockages against unchanging current levels is facilitated by the robust structure of the α -hemolysin protein, which results in an unitary conductance thanks to the lack of mobility.

Other examples of protein pores used for sensing are the porins such as the OmpG porin (a monomeric pore from the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria)²⁷ and the MspA pore from *Mycobacterium smegmatis*²⁷ or peptide antibiotics such as gramicidin and alamethicin.²⁹⁻³¹

Insertion in lipid bilayers

The most often used biological nanochannel is the α -hemolysin protein channel. The typical sensor resulted from this nanostructure consists of a single channel embedded within a lipid bilayer membrane. Traditionally, lipid bilayers are formed across 30-100 μ m sized orifices in polysulfone, Delrin, Teflon, or other hydrophobic polymer-based membranes.³² Then a single pore is inserted by adding the protein solution to the chamber filled which is filled with the electrolyte.

In order to solve problems related to the lack of precise control of the channel insertion, alternatives consisting on the use of a hand-operated hydrogel probes which can be coated with a layer of proteins and mechanically engaged with the lipid bilayer have been more recently reported.^{33,34} Furthermore, the stability of the bilayer has been improved by using soft or hard support structures. For example, supports made of soft hydrogels have been tested with photopolymerisable polymers,³⁵ poly(ethylene glycol),³⁶ and agarose gel.³⁷ Finally, the reduced diffusion and convection-based transport of analyte molecules through the support layer is also improved using solid supports, *i.e.* comprising the covalent linking of the bilayer to a support made of gold.^{39,39} Solid support structures have also been implemented without chemical linkage, using porous alumina to stabilize pore-suspended lipid bilayers.⁴⁰ In order to obtain a tight interface between the membrane and alumina, polymer cushion between the solid support and lipid bilayer was used.⁴¹

Biosensing using biological ion-channels: Stochastic sensing

Sensing principle

A single nanochannel based platform can be used as resistive-pulse sensor for the detection of molecular and macromolecule analytes. The resistive-pulse method, which when applied to such analytes is sometimes called stochastic sensing, entails mounting the membrane containing the nanochannel between two electrolyte solutions, applying a transmembrane potential difference, and measuring the resulting ion current flowing through the electrolyte-filled nanochannel. The structure and the physical processes affecting the ions diffusion on biomimetic natural ion channels have been extensively studied in the last decade.⁴²⁻⁴⁷

In simplest terms, when the analyte enters and translocates the nanochannel, it transiently blocks the ion current, resulting in a downward current pulse. In fact, the transport of molecules across membranes is a key mechanism for many life processes. Molecules are usually very long (*i.e.* DNA, RNA, proteins) in comparison with the diameter of the channels in the membranes which difficult their pass as a single unit, provoking their translocation through the channels. Translocation is a complicated process whose dynamics are strongly affected by a variety of parameters such as the

membrane thickness, membrane adsorption, electrochemical potential gradients, chemical potential gradients and assisting molecular motors between others.

From the sensing point of view, the translocation of a molecule through a channel modifies the channel electrical impedance, changing the ionic current which can be recorded and related to the molecule (analyte) and its concentration. Concretely, the mean duration and amplitude of the events is related with the identity of the analyte, while the frequency of occurrence of the events can be related with its concentration⁴⁸ (Figure 2A).

Detection of DNA, proteins and other analytes

The specificity of these natural protein pore based sensors to a high variety of analytes can be achieved through the insertion of specific receptors using genetic engineering fabrication techniques. For example, metal ions can be detected after the insertion of histidines by amino acid replacement or substitution,⁴⁹ while single-stranded DNA and proteins can be detected after the immobilization of the corresponding bioreceptors on engineered nanochannels, including also genetically encoded sensor elements.⁵⁰

The DNA hybridization event can be detected by covalently attaching inside the pore the oligonucleotide probe complementary to the target with interest to be detected. The DNA duplex formation produces a change in the ionic current which allows to identify the target ssDNA strand even at single-base resolution.^{51,52} The resolution of the currents associated with individual nucleotides can be improved by immobilizing DNA strands inside the α -hemolysin pore through terminal hairpins or biotin-streptavidin complexes.^{53,54}

In the DNA analysis field, it deserves to be highlighted the efforts in the development of nanopore-based microRNA. Outstanding is the work recently reported by Wang *et al.*⁵⁵ where a α -hemolysin pore is used to selectively detect microRNAs at the single molecular level in plasma samples from lung cancer patients without the need to use labels or microRNA amplification. By using oligonucleotide probes, microRNA is captured in the pore generating a target-specific signature signal which allows to quantify subpicomolar levels of cancer-associated microRNAs and distinguish single-nucleotide differences between microRNA family members.

Regarding the protein detection, one important problem found was related to the large proteins length which difficult their binding within the lumen of the α -hemolysin pore, so it was necessary a system able to detect binding events occurring outside the pore. Several approaches have been reported trying to solve this, by using *i.e.* polymers bound within the pore but with a free ligand able to recognize proteins out of the pore. In this case, the protein recognition produces a decrease in the fluctuations of the polymer within the pore, registering a decrease in the current noise.⁵⁶ Other approaches used disaccharides attached close to the entrance of the pore, which are able to detect lectins by registering a decrease in the ionic current.⁵⁷ Other alternative strategy consisted in immobilizing inhibitor peptides close to the entrance of the α -hemolysin pore, being the modified pore able to detect protein kinases through the blockage in the registered current.^{50,58} Of special relevance is the approach very recently reported by Bayley and co-workers using aptamers as bioreceptors.⁵⁹ They first covalently attached to a single cysteine residue near a mouth of the pore, a oligonucleotide complementary to the aptamer through a disulfide bond. The aptamer was immobilized through the hybridization reaction and then they observed that the presence of thrombin in the sample gave rise to the formation of cation-stabilized quadruplex, which changed the ionic current through the pore, allowing to detect thrombin at nanomolar levels.

Furthermore, it must be highlighted that nanoscale channels have also been used, in a minor extent, as useful tools for single molecule analysis of DNA or RNA processing enzymes^{60,61} and to study peptides and unfolding of proteins.⁶²⁻⁶⁴ Finally, non-covalent adapters can also be used to create binding sites for the detection of drugs and organic solvents.⁶⁵

Potential tool for DNA sequencing

One of the more exciting perspectives in this field is the potential ability of the α -hemolysin nanopore for DNA sequencing. DNA single strands could be electrophoretically driven through the α -hemolysin pore⁶⁶ and pass in an elongated conformation generating a 'finger print' like blocking of the ionic current which would be specific for each strand. The transit time and extent of the current could reveal information about the length of the nucleic acid and its base composition^{21,67,68} (Figure 2B). On the other hand, the magnitude of the conductance changes could give additional

details such as the presence of mismatches in DNA sequences. A key advantage of nanopore sequencing would be that it could detect nucleotides directly, without reagents or labeling, from a single molecule of single-stranded DNA, in contrast with the established techniques that require the use of fluorescent or luminescent labels, even also requiring the DNA amplification by the polymerase chain reaction. Furthermore, nanopore based analysis is also potentially capable of sequencing much longer continuous strands of DNA than other techniques. This is of great importance for the analysis of long-range genomic complexity which is related to cancer and other diseases.

However, for the successfully achievement of these purposes, a method of controlled translocation of the strand through the channel is needed together with a system able to solve the problems related to the fragility of the bilayer membrane that houses the nanochannel and the too short life-time of these membranes (only few hours before rupture).⁶⁹

The membrane fragility problem has been very recently solved by approaches using hybrid biological/solid-state ion channels formed by a channel-forming protein set in synthetic material.⁷⁰ In this context, Oxford Nanopore Technologies® has very recently presented a commercial system (GridION platform) which combines the α -hemolysin pore (inserted in synthetic materials) with the use of processive enzymes which ratchet DNA through the pore, showing that the method can be used to read lengths of many tens of kilobases. They have overcome also the problem derived from the fact that when a DNA polymer passes through a nanopore, a number of individual DNA bases occupy the aperture of the nanopore at any time. This company has engineered bespoke nanopores and data analysis algorithms to translate the characteristic electronic signals into DNA sequence data. The same company has also developed an alternative strategy based in the use of exonucleases enzymes which cleave individual DNA bases from a DNA strand.⁷¹ Since the unmodified α -hemolysin channel is not able to differentiate DNA bases, they chemically modified the nanochannel by covalent attachment of cyclodextrin, which acts as a binding site for individual DNA bases and allows accurate measurement of their passage through the nanopore binding.

To improve the efficiency of these nanochannel sensors, Bayley and co-workers⁷² have also recently reported the concept of a multi-base recognition sites in a single α -hemolysin nanopore, using two reading heads (R1 and R2) instead of only one. The current signal can consequently offer information about two positions in the sequence. It means that each base is read twice, first at R1 and secondly at R2 improving the overall quality of sequencing.

Based in all these principles, third generation sequencing platforms have recently been commercialized by that and other companies, taking also advantage of labeling technologies⁷³ (Figure 2C).

Sensing with arrays of biological ion channels

A single nanochannel is an excellent system for studying transport properties of different ions or molecules since the behavior of a single channel can be observed directly, without having to average the effects of multiple channels. However, as a single nanochannel can probe only a single molecule at a time, strategies for manufacturing arrays of nanochannels able to detect different molecules and simultaneously monitoring them are strongly required. The difficulty here of simultaneous measurement of the ionic current in a high number of channels on the same membrane limits this kind of multianalytes detection. From the few examples of biological nanochannel arrays used for electrochemical biosensing, it is outstanding the work done by Osaki *et al.*⁷⁴ which is in fact also one of the few examples of application of the stochastic sensing principle to nanochannel arrays. They reported a microarray system that enables simultaneous monitoring of multiple ionic currents through transmembrane α -hemolysin nanopores arrayed at bilayer lipid membranes (Figure 3). The developed system is able to detect translocation events of nucleic acid molecules, opening the way to further high-throughput applications. However, the difficulty to create homogeneous arrays has limited their application for routine analysis.

As conclusion of this first part of the review, it can be stated that in spite of the advantages of the biological ion channels in terms of sensitivity, selectivity and ability for the analysis of a variety of analytes, next generation of these sensing devices are likely to use nanochannels generated from

synthetic materials, the so called solid-state nanochannels, which are previewed to improve more not only the cost but also the scale of analyses.

SOLID-STATE NANOCHANNELS

As stated before, next generation of biosensing systems using nanochannels take advantage of artificial nanochannels embedded in a chemically and mechanically robust synthetic membrane. Moreover, the length-control that can be exerted on their fabrication allows to improve parameters related to the signal detection and quantitative analyses by simple changing the length of the channel.^{19,75} In addition, their size and shape can also be controlled in a precise way *i.e.* by metered penetration or ion track-etching technology, giving rise to conditions quite similar to the physiological ones. Furthermore, most of the developed methodologies for the generation of solid-state ion channels give rise to arrays of nanochannels (nanoporous membranes). This opens the way to novel large-scale real-world biosensing systems, different to those based in the concept of the Coulter counter, but with enormous potential not only due to electrochemical detection but also taking advantage of optical properties of such materials. In the following sections, the main methodologies for the preparation of both single/arrays of solid-state nanochannels for biosensing applications, their characterization methodologies and both electrical and optical applications are detailed.

Preparation of solid-state nanochannels

The traditional basic methods for the preparation of porous materials consist in: i) aggregation of particles; ii) subtraction of a component from a compact body; iii) structural changes like crystallisation and iv) inflation of a structure, for example by swelling. There are also some special methods such as: i) compaction of powder; ii) chemical reaction and precipitation; iii) crystallization and iv) thermal treatment.

However, only few of these basic methods were found useful for the fabrication of nanochannel-based sensors. The suitable materials are limited due to the requirements of stability, robustness,

possibility of (bio)functionalization and control of the pore size and distribution. In this context, the implementation of metal nanoporous polymer materials by electroless deposition made by Martin and co-workers,⁷⁶ and followed recently by other groups using electron-beam evaporation⁷⁷ and ion sputtering,⁷⁸ opened the way to an extensive research in this field, being the most successful strategies the following: i) track-etching on polymeric membranes; ii) ion beam sculpting: focused ion beam (FIB) and dual FIB/SEM systems; iii) electron-beam lithography on Si membranes; iv) nanopore electrodes fabrication from Pt wires; v) metallic substrates anodization; vi) micromolding techniques using polymers as masks and vii) formation of mesoporous thin films from nanoparticles deposition on solid surfaces. The obtained nanochannels are often modified with other materials, being of special novelty their modification with graphene which takes advantage of the properties of this nanostructured material.^{79,80}

Track-etching on polymeric membranes

The pioneered method to produce both single/arrays of solid-state nanochannels was the track-etch method. The variations of this method and the use of membranes made of a variety of materials were recently rightly summarized by Gyurcsány,⁸¹ so we only highlight here the main aspects related to this method.

The pioneer works used as template material commercially available polycarbonate track-etch membranes of around 6 μm thickness. This method consists in bombarding the membrane with a collimated beam of high-energy nuclear fission fragments⁸² or with ion beams from accelerators to create parallel damage tracks. The damage tracks are then etched into monodisperse pores by exposing the tracked film to a solution of aqueous base (Figure 4A, left). The diameter of the pore is determined by the etch time and the etch-solution temperature and the pore density is determined by the exposure time to the fission fragment beam. Membranes obtained with this method are nowadays commercially available, containing pores with diameters down to 10 nm and pore densities of approximately 6×10^8 pores cm^{-2} .

Multi-channel nanopores of application in biosensing can also be prepared in other materials such as anodized Al_2O_3 (AAO),⁸³⁻⁸⁵ SiO_2/SiN ⁸⁶ and mesoporous silica MCM-41⁸⁷ as explained in following sections.

A great enhancement in the rate of transport through the membrane can be obtained using conical nanochannels⁸⁸ instead of cylindrical ones. These conical shapes are obtained doing an asymmetric etching putting only one side of the membrane in contact with the etchant (Figure 4A, right). The geometry and size of the cones has been controlled following different strategies such as the addition of additives⁸⁹ or the application of hydrostatic pressure.⁹⁰ These conical nanochannels can be filled with, for example, gold in order to obtain gold nanoelectrodes with radii down to 2 nm⁹¹ (Figure 4B).

However, these track-etch membranes do not offer pore sizes in the range 10–100 nm where the most interesting nanomaterial properties are exhibited. Moreover, these templates do not offer much control over the morphology of the nanostructures synthesized in them; the pores are randomly distributed and are rather toothpick shaped with correspondingly difficult control and understanding of the nanomaterial properties synthesized in them. In addition to the above disadvantages, these materials are expensive to produce and attempts to rectify the morphological disadvantages have only led to increased production costs.

The physicochemical modification of the inner surface of track-etched polymer nanochannels is of key importance for further biosensing applications. Modification with metals such as Au and Pt (by electroless deposition, ion sputtering and electron-beam evaporation) or polymers (by initiated chemical vapor deposition and plasma) as well as the final introduction of biomolecules such DNA and antibodies have been extensively reported. These modifications after symmetric/asymmetric design for the shape of nanochannels have been very recently summarized and described in detail by Jiang's group⁹², so will not be considered in this review.

Electron beam lithography and Ion beam sculpting: focused ion beam (FIB) and dual FIB/SEM systems

Another approach with a high degree of pore-size control consists in the electron beam lithographic generation of the pores on *i.e.* Si membranes⁹³ taking advantage of high energy electron beam provided *i.e.* by commercial TEM/SEM devices. In spite of the advantages of this technique in terms of the high resolution achieved, it has the limitations of the slow serial process and the small area that can be patterned.

An important step here in single solid-state nanochannel fabrication was made with development of the ion-beam sculpting method which bridges nanochannel sensing and well established materials and procedures used in microelectronics.⁹⁴ Nanochannels generated using the focused ion beam (FIB) milling can be tailored down to less than 5 nm in diameter.⁹⁵ A variety of noble gas ions and ion beam fluxes (He, Ne, Ar, Kr, and Xe) have been used to drastically change some of the potentially relevant parameters of the process.⁹⁶

The actual FIB machines are increasingly equipped also with an electron beam (the so-called dual-beam or cross-beam machines), that allows the electron beam to be used also for imaging, like in conventional SEMs.^{97,98} A mini-RF driven plasma source can be used to generate focused ion beam with various ion species. A two-lens electron column can be used for SEM imaging, and finally an axis manipulator system can be used for sample positioning. This kind of integrated FIB/SEM dual-beam system not only helps to improve the accuracy and reproducibility when performing ion beam sculpting, but also enables to perform cross-sectioning, imaging, and analysis with the same tool. The main advantage of this approach is the ability to produce a wide variety of ion species tailored to the application. In this context, the implementation of helium ion microscope (HeIM) as a potential technique for precise nanopatterning is one of the main latest innovation in this area,⁹⁹ related to its ability to mill and sputter soft materials, in particular, low atomic number materials with extremely low rates with an extremely small probe size in the order of 0.5 nm.

Although the perspectives are promising, the high cost and times of production of these techniques minimize their extensive use for nanochannels fabrication and further biosensing purposes.

Nanopore electrodes fabrication from Pt wires

In contrast with the single solid-state nanochannels fabricated in a free-standing form, the nanopore electrodes fabricated from Pt wires have only one end of the nanopore opened to the solution whereas the other end is backed by the electrode material. Such nanopore electrodes are fabricated by sealing an electrochemically etched Pt wire into a glass capillary, being then the glass polished finally the generated Pt disk (diameter of around 15–100 nm) electrochemically etched back.¹⁰⁰

The advantages of this design include the simplicity and reproducibility of fabrication, a built-in signal transduction element (the Pt electrode) for monitoring molecular transport through the pore and the portability and mechanical robustness of the solid electrode.

Metallic substrates anodization

Other very interesting fabrication technique consists in the nanochannels array generation on metallic substrates, being the most representative one the generation of such nanochannels on aluminum. A typical fabrication process¹⁰¹ consists in the anodization of aluminum of high purity in an acidic solution applying a constant high voltage. Under these conditions, aluminum oxide is generated, containing many surface irregularities (defects) where the electric field concentrates. This localized electric field enhances acidic dissolution of the oxide at the bottom of the pores while leaving the pore walls intact, resulting in the nanochannels formation. The barrier layer produced at the bottom of the pore channels is subsequently removed by immersion in dilute acid during which the pores are also enlarged. The anodization under optimized conditions gives rise to the production of porous alumina with a highly ordered cell configuration. Moreover, a two-step anodization process for fabricating self-ordered porous alumina templates, has been pioneered by Masuda's group.¹⁰² These Al₂O₃ membranes with a variety of pore sizes are nowadays commercially available

and their advantageous properties have made possible their extensive use for biosensing applications, as will be detailed in the *applications* section.

An exciting alternative of special interest also for later biosensing applications consists in the generation of Al₂O₃ nanochannels directly on the surface of an electrotransducer surface has been recently reported by Foong *et al.*,¹⁰³ after depositing an aluminum layer by chemical vapor deposition (Figure 4C). However, the use of this kind of high vacuum techniques are expensive and time-consuming. An alternative that overcome these drawbacks consists on the *in-situ* electrodeposition of the aluminum on the surface of electrotransducer. Unfortunately, the electrodeposition of aluminium from metal aqueous solution is not possible, due to the hydrogen discharge produced at the high negative potentials needed (below -1.67 V vs NHE). In order to solve this, ionic liquids, a new class of compounds characterized by high conductivity, low vapor pressures and wide electrochemical window were found as ideal media for the electroreduction of highly positive metals which cannot be electrodeposited from aqueous media. In this way, 1-butyl-3-methyl-imidazolium heptachloroaluminate¹⁰⁴ and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolim chloride¹⁰⁵ were used as source of aluminum for its electrodeposition on carbon steel and further generation of nanochannels by anodization. However, in spite of the above mentioned advantages it deserves to be pointed out that the aluminum electrodeposition from ionic liquids requires a dry atmosphere to avoid the presence of H₂O in the liquid, being this a handicap for a routine fabrication.

Finally, other example of metal substrates anodization that deserves to be mentioned consists in the preparation of an alloy of nickel, electrolytic aluminium and rhenium pellets, melting under inert atmosphere and drop casting into a cylindrical copper mould.¹⁰⁶ Then, the production of nanochannel arrays is performed by electrochemical anodization/dissolution of the Rhenium fibers, obtaining the pores. Furthermore, metals like gold can be deposited inside them to give a nanoelectrode array that might prove to be useful in electrochemical sensors.

Micromolding techniques

- Micromolding from PDMS

Artificial nanochannel arrays for molecular sensing can also be fabricated with great ease and control using micromolding techniques. Well-established lithographic techniques are used to create a negative master of the pore and reservoirs, which is subsequently cast into a poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) slab, as done by Saleh *et al.*¹⁰⁷ They created the negative of the pore on silicon substrates by patterning a 200 nm sized (wide and thick) polystyrene line using electron-beam lithography and then used photolithography to pattern a photoresist (SU-8) on the substrate so as to form the negatives of the reservoirs. The outstanding durability of both polystyrene and SU-8 after the cross-linking allows to reuse the masters indefinitely.

- Micromolding from block copolymers

An improvement of the previous approach consists in the fabrication of well-defined nanostructures for nanopatterning using self-assembly of block copolymers (BCPs), which is of great interest due to the flexibility, simplicity and low-cost of the process together with the possibility of tuning the dimensions and chemical properties. Many potential applications of BCP thin films to different nanotechnologies, such as the BCP lithography,¹⁰⁸ nanoparticle template,¹⁰⁹ nanoarray¹¹⁰ and nanoporous thin film¹¹¹ have been developed. Poly(methylmethacrylate) (PMMA) homopolymers¹¹² and polystyrene-*b*-polydimethylsiloxane (PS-PDMS) block copolymers have been recently used for the formation of well-oriented cylinders with perpendicular morphology.¹¹³

As it has been mentioned, these emerging materials have enormous potential but it must be taken into account the easy formation of cracks and film delamination, problems that must be solved for the massive implantation of this fabrication method.

- Soft lithographic molding: nanoimprint lithography

The recent advances and improvements in the soft lithographic molding in terms of both the absolute sizes and aspect ratios of molded features that it can generate have made this technique an interesting alternative for the production of nanochannel arrays. Based on these fundamentals,

Aizenberg and co-workers have demonstrated that replica molding can be used to transfer an array of high-aspect-ratio nanoposts from silicon to epoxy, through a PDMS intermediate¹¹⁴ and also that, in combination with nanoskiving, these high-aspect-ratio structures provide a basis for the fabrication of arrays of significantly smaller and more complex structures, and in greater numbers of replicas.¹¹⁵ The initial drawback of the cost of defining a master with nanostructures for soft lithography is offset by the ease and low cost of producing *i.e.* PDMS replicas for further experiments to fabricate nanostructures, which has allowed the implementation of the nanoimprint lithography¹¹⁶⁻¹¹⁸ as a robust technique for nanochannels generation. Of special interest is the nanotransfer print concept very recently reported by Rogers and co-workers.¹¹⁹ It consists on the use of stamps prepared on silicon wafers anisotropically etched through polymeric masks, defined by soft nanoimprint lithography, and final nanotransfer printing onto PDMS target substrates. In this way they obtain 3D nanochannels on flexible substrates in a simple way and with mass production possibilities (Figure 5A).

However, in spite of the promising perspectives, other limitations have to be considered such as the softness of the PDMS that can cause distortions in printed or molded structures and its non-stability in many organic solvents or at high temperatures.

Highly-ordered mesoporous thin films formation

The use of highly-ordered mesoporous and macroporous thin films coating solid electrode surfaces has a great potential application in electrochemical analysis.¹²⁰ Strategies such as the use of self-assembled nanoparticle templates¹²¹ self-assembled surfactant templates¹²² and hard templating/nanocasting approaches¹²³ have been followed in the last years in order to get ordered nanochannel array films on electrodes.

- Nanoparticles assembling

The first strategy consists on assembling of nanoparticles in a well-controlled way. The simplest approach is based on a simple evaporation of a thin film of nanoparticles suspension on the horizontal electrode surface under well-controlled conditions of temperature and humidity, obtaining

locally well-organized structures. This method is therefore suitable for modifying electrodes with a small geometric surface area, as is the case for ultramicroelectrodes, but for electrodes with surface area larger than mm^2 vertical deposition is more suitable, allowing much better control of defect density. A very interesting variation of this technique consists in the so-called nanosphere lithography (NSL). It is of special interest the work very recently reported by Wang *et al.*¹²⁴ consisting on the formation of a highly ordered and hierarchically structured anodic aluminum oxide template by pre-patterning first an aluminum substrate surface with a nanoindentation array *via* polystyrene nanospheres lithography and finally performing an anodization treatment (Figure 5B).

Furthermore, the interstitial space between the beads can be filled with conducting material such as metals¹²⁵ carbon¹²⁶ and polymers¹²⁷ using electrodeposition and electropolymerization. The subsequent removal of the template results in the final porous structure, which is a perfect negative copy of the template.

The great advantages of this method in terms of simplicity, low cost and versatility are minimized due to the formation of intrinsic defects observed at large scale inducing irreproducibility in the further sensing applications.

- Surfactant templates assembling and hard templating/nanocasting approaches

Highly-ordered mesoporous metallic films can be generated by electrodeposition utilizing lyotropic liquid-crystalline phases of non-ionic surfactants (*i.e.* polyethylene oxides) as a direct physical cast to template the mesostructure.¹²⁸ (Figure 5D). Furthermore, ordered mesoporous carbons with various pore structures can also be produced by a nanocasting process using mesostructured silica samples with a specific pore topology as secondary templates,¹²⁹ which involves the infiltration of a carbon precursor into the pores followed by transformation into a rigid carbon structure by pyrolysis and the removing of the silica template to obtain the mesoporous carbon replica.

Other interesting materials used for such application are porous silica (PSi) photonic architectures such as single and double layered Fabry-Pérot films¹³⁰ and more complex multilayer Bragg mirrors,¹³¹ rugate filters¹³² and microcavities.¹³³

These approaches take advantage of the diverse structure and dimension of the template materials and the possibility to design the chemical composition and structure. However, there are still remain challenges in their use arising from some inherent disadvantages related to the costly precursors needed and the required conditions of high temperature and inert environmental, which also increase the operational costs and the time of the process, limiting the mass production.

Characterization of solid-state nanochannels

The main methods used for the characterization of nanochannels, always from the perspective of the later biosensing applications interest will be described in this section. Although most of the methods are described here for the characterization of solid-state nanochannels, almost all of them are also valid for the study of biological ion channels.

Imaging characterization

The thickness of the membrane as well as the pore size and shape (also their density and distribution in the case of nanochannel arrays) are crucial parameters needed to be accurately controlled in order to assure a good and reproducible performance of the derived sensing systems. Imaging techniques such as atomic force microscopy (AFM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) give an estimation of all these parameters in a rapid and easy way. AFM¹³⁴ can be only used to observe the membranes surface but has the advantage of no requirements on the conductivity of samples and its high resolution below the nanometer level. FESEM^{135,136} is widely used to observe the surface and cross-sections, and measure the thickness of different samples but requires good electrical conductivity, problem that can be solved sputtering conductive layers. Finally, TEM^{137,138} can be used to observe cross-sections and morphology and also to characterize composition and crystalline structures. These techniques, mainly SEM, are routinely used for a preliminary characterization of nanochannels, being remarkable the thorough characterization studies of typical porous anodic alumina membranes recently reported by Zhu *et al.*¹³⁹ using AFM, TEM and FESEM, obtaining useful information about different channels generation strategies (Figure 6).

The main advantages of the nanochannels analysis by AFM compared with the one performed using electron microscopy techniques are related with the ability of providing higher resolution, 3D surface profile and the non-necessity of neither special treatments (such as carbon/metal coatings) that could damage the membranes nor expensive vacuum environment. However, the AFM analysis has the well-known limitations related to the single scan image size (max. scanning area of about 150×150 micrometers in one pass), the low scanning speed and the possibility of obtaining image artifacts induced by unsuitable tips, between others.

Electrochemical characterization

It is known that the conductance of the pores depends on membrane voltage, and the kind of this dependence is related to the radius of the pore. More in detail, the nanopore current depends on the shape of the pore,¹⁴⁰ the pH of the solution,¹⁴¹ the distribution of surface charges,¹⁴² and the chemical composition of the ions.¹⁴³

The dependence of the nanopore biosensor conductance signal on its shape is a very important factor to be taken into account. The 3D shape of a nanopore allows for modeling its conductance on a wide range of ionic strengths. Furthermore, recent studies¹⁴⁴ have demonstrated that the dependence of the nanopore conductance on ionic strength can be used to obtain precise information about the nanopore shape, avoiding the use of time-consuming imaging analysis, being a reliable methodology to monitor and evaluate changes in the nanopore shape during electrical measurements.

From the biosensing point of view, the analytes diffusion through the nanochannels and the effect of the charges of both analytes and channels on this diffusion are fundamental parameters that have been studied through electrochemical measurements of resistance, conductance, voltammetry or Z-potential. As the Coulter counter concept is the basis of the sensing using single nanochannels, the characterization of such device (in the micrometric scale) is a good starting point to understand the behaviour of the nanometric devices.¹⁴⁵

The electromechanical coupling due to the electrical charge separations at interfaces is of great importance in microfluidics being this kind of coupling exploited, for example, in the electro-osmotic reactant delivery in the total microanalysis systems.¹⁴⁶ Some of these macroscopic

characteristics are still valid when changing from micro- to nanofluidics due the fact that the system dimensions are much larger than the molecular scale. The remarkable new phenomena expected to be found in the nanoscale are the formation of polarization due to mechano- and electrochemical couplings as well as the appearance of surface conductivity due to counterions electrostatically adsorbed. Those phenomena must be carefully considered while studying the transport properties of fine-porous membranes. In such membranes the analytes transference between channels is electrically implemented so that electro-osmosis is of great importance. In this context, the so-called zeta potential, which controls the electromechanical coupling, is of crucial importance. In porous media, the zeta potentials are obtained through the measurements of streaming potential¹⁴⁷ but these measurements by themselves don't give a direct estimation of the zeta potential, due to the interference exerted by electric layers overlapping. Due to all that, electric conductivity has been extensively used as parameter to control the etching process,¹⁴⁸ and in combination with streaming potential measurements they also have been applied for the extraction of detailed information about the electrochemical properties of nanoporous membranes¹⁴⁹ finding that the limiting current densities for a nanofluidic system are two orders of magnitude lower than the normal values found in microfluidic ones with electro-osmotic fluid delivery, being this an important handicap that must be taken into account in the application of such nanofluidic elements in microsystems.

The presence of charges in both analytes and nanochannels walls is a crucial parameter that affect the nanochannels based sensing systems. The formation of the charges at a nanochannel inner wall is due to dissociation of surface groups or the adsorption of charged molecules from the solution.¹⁵⁰ The relative ratio between wall surface/channel bulk volume increases when the channel width decrease giving rise to some adsorption effects. Consequently, the molecular and ionic species present in nanochannels suffer stronger interactions with the inner walls. The electric double layers formed at the inner walls can fill substantial parts of the nanochannels, which strongly affects the transport of molecules, the fluid flow and the electric current.¹⁵¹ In this context, reported conductance models in nanochannels with charged walls,¹⁵² demonstrate that relatively small concentration of wall charges dramatically reduces the self-energy transport barrier. These

phenomena must be carefully considered by further applications of nanoporous materials in biosensing.

Simple voltammetric measurements can also be performed for the characterization of nanoporous materials. For example, cylindrical nanochannels of 50 nm in diameter fabricated from track-etched polycarbonate membranes on gold films were characterized by Ito *et al.*¹⁵³ using cyclic voltammetry (CV) (Figure 7). The CV measurements showed the transition from linear to radial diffusion modes of redox-active species with decreasing scan rate. The resulting change in maximum faradaic current, which is the peak current in a peak-shaped CV and the plateau current in a sigmoidal CV, provides a simple means for calculating the pore length and effective pore density. Furthermore, nanopore electrodes fabricated from Pt wires were also voltammetrically characterized by White's group,¹⁵⁴ performing computer simulations and detailing the steady-state response of the nanopore electrode.

Finally, it deserves to be highlighted the coupling of both electrochemical and optical measurements recently reported by Perry *et al.*¹⁵⁵ monitoring also the ion transport nanofluidic funnels by measuring the fluorescence of fluorescein molecule flowing through the channels, opening the way to dual measurements of interest for many applications.

Nuclear magnetic resonance and X-ray diffraction characterizations

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopic techniques have been used to investigate the structure and adsorption properties of porous metal-organic materials.^{156,157} These techniques can give useful information about the shape and size of the cavities in nanoporous materials.¹⁵⁸ For example, NMR spectroscopy is one of the most powerful techniques used for the characterization of the porous structure and the sorption mechanism in sorbents such as zeolite, organic host, and silica-based mesoporous materials.^{159,160} In particular, multinuclear, two-dimensional (2D) solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, which is sensitive to interatomic distances and dynamics, allows to characterize molecular structures.¹⁶¹

Furthermore, the spectroscopy of spin-active gases diffused to the nanochannels can also give useful information about the shape and size of the nanochannels. For example, Xenon NMR

spectroscopy has been used for the characterization of nanoporous materials.¹⁶² By continuous flow technique, Xe can be continuously delivered to the sample allowing the recording of 2D exchange spectra and collecting information on the accessibility of the nanochannels.

It can be stated that NMR techniques can be used in a complementary way so as to obtain a complete map of the analyzed material. In this context, Comotti *et al.*¹⁶³ reported the combination of multinuclear solid state ¹²⁹Xe NMR, together with synchrotron X-ray diffraction and adsorption to investigate the structural relationship and adsorption properties of an Al³⁺ microporous coordination polymer with straight 1D channels. 2D solid state NMR spectroscopy, including ¹H-¹³C, also revealed the arrangement of the framework (Figure 8A). However, in spite of the above mentioned advantages, NMR techniques are not extensively used for nanochannels characterizations, due to their limitations related to the expensive and time consuming analysis, that includes the relatively long period of times necessary for the interpretation of the spectra.

Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction¹⁶⁴ is also a powerful technique also used for the characterization of nanoporous materials. This technique uses small incident angles for the incoming X-ray so that diffraction can be made surface sensitive. It is used to study surfaces and layers because wave penetration is limited in the order of nanometers. This is the case of the work reported by Malachias *et al.*¹⁶⁵ where X-ray grazing-incidence diffraction was used to confirm the crystalline quality of nanochannel networks fabricated by etching techniques (Figure 8B). However, the use of this powerful technique is limited to only materials with low stress gradient, due to the variability of the penetration depth which depends on the incident angle.

Other characterizations

In addition to the detailed above, several other techniques, such as ellipsometric porosimetry¹⁶⁶ and X-ray porosimetry,¹⁶⁷ have been established over the last decade as capable metrologies to characterize pores in sub-micron thin films. These techniques are based on a variety of physics interaction between the probe and the pores. Both porosimetry techniques give useful information about the pore metrics in determined materials but none of them is totally comprehensive for a full characterization of the pores. In this context depth-profiled positronium annihilation lifetime

spectroscopy (PALS) emerged as a unique porosimetry technique with broad applicability in the characterization of nanoporous materials.^{168,169} PALS employs positrons, the antiparticle of electrons, to probe the pore structure of materials. Depth profiling with PALS has been proposed as an alternative methodology to study depth-dependent changes in porous structures without damaging the sample by injecting the positrons *i.e.* into porous films as reported by Peng *et al.*¹⁷⁰ However, this technique strongly depends on model assumption and is not accurate for pore size of less than 10 nm.

Finally, another technique used in a very much lower extent but that deserves to be highlighted, is the scanning ion conductance microscopy (SICM). This technique can be used to interrogate ion currents emanating from nanometer scale pores of a polymer membrane as recently reported by Chen *et al.*¹⁷¹ They measure the transport activity of individual pores by evaluating ion current images and simultaneously record the corresponding topographic images, concluding that nanoscale transport properties can be accurately measured with SICM.

Integration into lab-on-a-chip platforms

Microfluidics and lab-on-a-chip systems have undergone enormous development during the past decade. The combination of such systems with nanochannels and other nanostructured platforms has opened the way to very promising integrated sensing devices.^{172,173}

The most common fabrication method for such devices involves the use of sacrificial layers to prepare the nanochannels directly on chip.¹⁷⁴ Using this strategy even vertical arrays of nanochannels have been reported.¹⁷⁵ Another suitable method takes advantage of elastomeric substrates, where the master is obtained introducing controllable cracks in an elastomer.¹⁷⁶ This method can be greatly simplified doing an injection molding of thermoplastic polymers, giving rise to well-defined nanofluidic systems in a single processing step.¹⁷⁷

The conditions however, have to be carefully optimized to obtain closed channels, as one of the major problems here is ceiling collapse, which blocks the nanochannels even during fabrication. There are only few examples of nanochannels on glass chips, due to the fact that the etching of glass

is mostly isotropic, as a result of which it is difficult to control the lateral dimensions of the channel in the nm range. In spite of these problems, the progress in this field has been far beyond the original micro total analytical systems because microfluidic devices are being used not only used as analytical systems but also as platforms for *i.e.* bioreactions. However, the microfluidics research field is still facing many challenges which are avoiding their analytical application, such as the improvement of both selectivity and sensitivity parameters.

Electrical based biosensing applications

Although the most reported way to approach nanochannels for biosensing with final electrochemical detection consists in the application of the above explained Coulter counter principle using single nanochannels, some recent works have also been focused on the use of nanochannel arrays, following in this case different sensing strategies, mostly based in the modification of conventional electrotransducer surfaces and measuring the changes in the electrochemical response of an electroactive specie in solution. In all cases, these sensing methodologies take advantage of the inherent properties of the electrical techniques, such as the short time and costs of analysis and the easy to use mode between others. Some typical electrical based applications related to the use of single nanochannels and the array like ones are discussed in the following sections.

Use of solid-state single nanochannels

A single nanochannel based platform, based on a synthetic or biological membrane, can be used as resistive-pulse sensor for the detection of molecular and macromolecule analytes. The resistive-pulse method, which when applied to such analytes is sometimes called stochastic sensing, entails mounting the membrane containing the nanochannel between two electrolyte solutions, applying a transmembrane potential difference, and measuring the resulting ion current flowing through the electrolyte-filled nanochannel. In simplest terms, when the analyte enters and translocates the nanochannel, it transiently blocks the ion current, resulting in a downward current pulse (as detailed in previous sections). The current-pulse frequency is proportional to the concentration of the analyte,

and the identity of the analyte is encoded in the current-pulse signature, as defined by the average magnitude and duration of the current pulses.

The structure and the physical processes affecting the ions diffusion on biomimetic natural ion channels have been extensively studied in the last decade.^{47,178-182}

- Solid-state single nanochannels functionalization

The functionalization of solid-state single nanochannels for further applications in most of the biosensing formats is a crucial step which is under extensively research. The biosensing capabilities of the nanochannels obviously depend on the surface characteristics of their inner walls to achieve the desired functionality of the biomimetic system. In addition to the classical functionalization methods, it deserves to be highlighted the novel approach recently reported by Ali *et al.*¹⁸³ to incorporate biosensing elements into polymer nanochannels by using electrostatic self-assembly. They used bifunctional macromolecular ligands to electrostatically assemble biorecognition sites into the walls of single conical nanochannels generated in poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) membranes, which then were used as recognition elements for biosensing, opening the way to improved systems based on polymeric membranes. It is also remarkable the recent approach reported by Jiang's group¹⁸⁴ based on the modification of a solid-state single nanochannel with β -cyclodextrin for the enantioselective recognition of histidine enantiomers through monitoring of ionic current signatures.

- DNA analysis

Cylindrical-shaped solid-state single nanopores generated in silicon nitride/oxide membranes by electron beam lithography/ion beam sculpting have been used to resolve sequences of individual DNA molecules linked to a degree of partial pore blockage by the DNA¹⁸⁵⁻¹⁸⁹ measuring changes in conductance during DNA translocation. Al_2O_3 substrates with pores generated by electron beam lithography¹⁹⁰ or ion-beam sculpting⁷⁹ have also been used for this purpose. From the works reporting this application deserve to be highlighted the improvements reported by Meller's group on SiN nanopores approaching the effect of the salt gradients.¹⁹¹ The same group¹⁹² has also recently

achieved the single-molecule detection of specific DNA sequences hybridizing double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) with peptide nucleic acid (PNA) probes and electrophoretically threading the DNA through sub-5 nm in diameter SiN pores, opening up a wide range of possibilities in human genomics as well as in pathogen detection for fighting infectious diseases. Furthermore, nanoporous gold prepared by selective dissolution of silver from silver/gold alloy has also been used to develop a DNA biosensor using multifunctional encoded DNA-Au bio bar codes.¹⁹³

In addition to the cylindrical ones, conical-shaped gold nanotubes have also been used for DNA analysis by Martin's group, achieving even mismatch selectivity.¹⁹⁴ and taking advantage of that geometry that offer a dramatic enhancement in the rate of transport through the membrane.

Finally, it deserves to be highlighted the very interesting work recently reported by Garaj *et al.*¹⁹⁵ related to the use of graphene membranes. They do electrical measurements on graphene membranes in which a single nanopore is drilled showing that the membrane's effective insulating thickness is less than one nanometer. This small effective thickness makes graphene a suitable substrate for very high resolution, high throughput nanopore-based single-molecule detectors, being successfully applied here for the DNA sequencing. The important achievements reported in this work seem to indicate that graphene based nanochannels offer new insights into atomic surface processes and sensor development opportunities.

- Protein detection

Cylindrical solid-state nanochannels are also capable of the label-free analysis of proteins. Of special interest is the very recent work reported by Wei *et al.*¹⁹⁶ where the use of metallized silicon nitride nanopores chemically modified with nitrilotriacetic acid receptors for the stochastic sensing of proteins is described. The authors found that reversible binding and unbinding of the proteins to the receptors can be monitored in real time and also demonstrated the versatile nature of this approach for His-tagged proteins detection. (Figure 9A). This kind of cylindrical-shaped solid-state single nanochannels in silicon nitride^{197,198} and also in polymeric¹⁹⁹ membranes have also been used by other authors for the study of proteins translocation.

On the other hand, conical-shaped nanochannels are ideally suited for resistive-pulse sensing applications, due to a focusing effect that makes ion current be focused towards the electrolyte solution at the tip opening of the nanochannel. For this reason, ion current is extremely sensitive to analyte species present in the tip of this kind of nanochannels. Thus, polymeric membranes have been used to generate these conical nanochannels by the track-etch method and applied for electrochemically detection of proteins^{183,200} Even single porphyrin molecules (a molecular analyte, opposed to a particle or macromolecule), have been sensed based on similar principles, using a conically shaped nanochannel prepared by the track-etch method as the sensing element as done by Martin's group.²⁰¹ They sensed the molecular analyte thanks to the small diameter opening of the conical nanochannel (up to 4.5 nm) which is comparable to the diameter of the analyte molecule (*i.e.* porphyrin which is up to 2 nm). Furthermore, conical nanochannels in polymeric membranes modified with metal-chelating ligands have been used for the detection of proteins such as lactoferrin, *via* the metal ion affinity-based biomolecular recognition²⁰² (Figure 9B).

Finally, conical gold nanotubes embedded within polymeric membranes have also been used, in a minor extent, for protein detection.²⁰³

- *Other analytes sensing*

In addition to the extensive use of solid-state single nanochannels in DNA and protein detection, other interesting applications of these sensing systems have been reported in the last years. This is the case of the biomimetic potassium responsive nanochannel closely imitating the *in vivo* condition recently developed by Hou *et al.*²⁰⁴ immobilizing G-quadruplex DNA onto a synthetic nanochannel embedded in a track etched polyethylene terephthalate membrane, undergoing a potassium-responsive conformational change and then inducing a change in the effective pore size. (Figure 10A). Other very recent interesting application which deserves to be highlighted is the possibility to use resistive pulse sensors for electrokinetic surface charge measurements of nanoparticles.²⁰⁵ It can be done by using flexible polyurethane membranes containing a single conical nanochannels and recording the particle blockade rate for different pressures applied across a pore sensor, thanks to the combination of the applied pressure with electro-osmosis and electrophoresis effects (Figure 10B).

Finally, we consider relevant to highlight the work done by White and co-workers^{206,207} who described the fabrication and electrochemical behavior of conical-shaped glass nanopore electrodes not only as platforms for investigating molecular transport through orifices of nanoscale dimensions but also as sensors after chemical modification. Furthermore, they also found that the cone-shaped glass nanopore structures were ideal for containing additional functional layers, such as ion-selective membranes. After these pioneering works, they reported a novel glass nanopore-based ion-selective electrode (ISE) for the detection of Cl⁻ ions in scanning electrochemical microscope experiments to map the ion flux through a micropore.²⁰⁸ They fabricated the all-solid-state ISE by sealing a conically etched platinum wire into a soda lime glass capillary and created the conical nanopore after polishing. Then they electroplated Ag on the Pt electrode in the pore and chlorinated to obtain a Ag/AgCl layer within the pore, resulting in a Ag/AgCl layer-coated ISE highly selective to Cl⁻.

Use of solid-state nanochannel arrays

- DNA analysis

Recent works are focused on the use of arrays of nanochannels as modifiers of conventional electrotransducer surfaces and measuring the changes of the electrochemical response of an electroactive specie in solution due to the presence of the analyte inside the channels. Al₂O₃ membranes prepared by anodization have a high pore density (1x10⁹/cm²) and small pore diameters, that results in a substrate with high surface area that can be easily functionalized being in consequence very advantageous for biosensing. These characteristics, together with their commercial availability have made them one of the preferred nanoporous substrates for biosensing applications. For example, hydroxyl groups on the Al₂O₃ surface can be used for chemical functionalization and join to amino groups of *i.e.* 5'-aminated DNA. This approach can be applied for DNA detection and separation. The surface charge effect in controlling ionic conductance through a nanoporous Al₂O₃ membrane has also been investigated by Smirnov's group for its application in the detection of unlabeled DNA.²⁰⁹ For example, nanoporous Al₂O₃ modified with covalently linked DNA has been used to detect target DNA by monitoring the increase in impedance at the electrode upon DNA hybridization, which results from blocking the channels to ionic flow.⁸⁴ Cyclic voltammetry, direct

current conductance, impedance spectroscopy and even electrical impedance²¹⁰ were the electrochemical techniques tested, and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-/3-}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+/3+}$ were the redox pairs used to probe the efficiency of ion blockage. After the covalent immobilization of the DNA probe inside the chemically modified nanochannels, the hybridization of target DNA takes place. For the electrical measurements, the back layer of aluminium under the membrane acts as working electrode and a polished aluminium rod as the counter electrode immersed in electrolyte solution above the membrane. The hybridization causes an increase in the electrical impedance in KCl solution by more than 50 %, being this change related with the biological event. The effect of both electrostatic and steric effects of the DNA duplex on the diffusion of electroactive species in similar approaches has been recently thoroughly studied.²¹¹

Our group has recently reported a novel device and methodology for the rapid and simple label-free electrochemical detection of ssDNA using screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) modified with nanoporous Al_2O_3 membranes.²¹² The membranes are functionalized with probe ssDNA, followed by the hybridization event that gives rise to the channel blocking. It was found that the blockage inside the nanochannels is fast and easy to be detected by measuring the decrease in the differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) peak current of the $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-/3-}$ redox specie used as indicator (Figure 11AB). Although one of the main advantages of the nanochannels based electrochemical sensing is that they are label-free systems, sometimes the limits of detection achieved are not enough to assure their further application for the detection of analytes in real samples. In this context, our group has also demonstrated that the use of 20-nm gold nanoparticle tags increase the blockage inside the nanochannels, improving in this way the sensitivity of the assay. For the use of nanoparticles as analytical tools in nanochannels arrays sensing systems there must be carefully considered the studies performed by White's group²¹³ related to the nanoparticle transport in nanochannels, where it is concluded that nanoparticle size can be differentiated based on pulse height, and to a lesser extent based on translocation time.

- Protein detection

The same principles of the DNA hybridization detection based on the blockage of the diffusion of electroactive species through the mentioned Al_2O_3 membranes to the SPCEs have been recently approached by our group for the rapid and simple label-free electrochemical detection of human IgG as model protein.²¹⁴ Furthermore, AuNPs were used as labels and also the silver catalytic deposition on the AuNPs labels was approached in order to obtain a higher blockage of the channels and improve more in this way the detection limits. The final optimized set up was applied for the detection of a breast cancer biomarker (CA15-3 protein) spiked in human blood samples, achieving clinical relevant detection limits and demonstrating a “dual” character of the membranes: as sensing platforms and also as “filters” minimizing matrix interferences thanks to size-exclusion effects (Figure 11C).²¹⁵ A similar approach has been very recently reported using even aptamers as bioreceptors for the detection of thrombin in blood.²¹⁶ This nanochannel/nanoparticle biosensing system would have enormous potential in future miniaturized designs adapted to mass production technologies such as screen-printing technology.

In addition to the Al_2O_3 membranes, other arrays of synthetic nanochannels have been used, in a minor extent, for protein sensing. This is the case of the ion channel biosensors constructed onto the surface of gold coated quartz crystal electrodes by Hou *et al.*²¹⁷ They immobilized on a gold electrode a positively charged metalloprotein which mimicked the section of a viral transmembrane glycoprotein with its pocket that is suitable for the binding of small molecules. The resulting sensor consequently acts as an artificial ion channel. The voltammetric signal of the system $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-/3-}$ is modulated by specific analyte binding to the coiled coil. The results indicate that nanomolar quantities of peptides and small molecules that bind in the hydrophobic pocket could be selectively detected, providing a method for label-free detection of binding to a viral transmembrane glycoprotein and opening promising perspectives.

Optical based biosensing applications

In addition to the extensive use in electroanalysis, powerful optical tools such as fluorescence, interferometry and photonics have been reported in the last years as reading techniques in nanochannel arrays based sensors. In addition to the possibility to detect optical labels, some nanoporous materials possess optical properties that can change during the presence of specific analytes in the inner walls of the nanochannels in label-free assays. The use of single nanochannels has not been extensively reported here, so it will not be considered in this review.

Consequently, in spite of the fact that the inherent drawbacks of the optical detection techniques (time and cost of analysis and necessity of labels in some cases) which have limited the implementation of these sensing systems compared with the electrical based ones, it deserves to pay attention to some interesting recent approaches that could open new perspectives on this field.

Fluorescence and photoluminescence detection

The most common fluorescence based biosensing approaches are focused on the detection of DNA, taking advantage of the use of Al_2O_3 membranes and fluorescent dyes. A representative example of a flow-through-type DNA array fabricated by fixing a single-stranded probe DNA to the inner walls of holes in an ideally ordered anodic porous Al_2O_3 substrate coated with a platinum layer was reported by Matsumoto *et al.*²¹⁸ They allowed the target DNA to flow through the holes and the DNA hybridization reaction gave rise to discrete, ordered spots of fluorescence emitted from each nanometer-scale hole. Porous Al_2O_3 was also employed by Ma *et al.*²¹⁹ as model chromatographic packing material for the depth-resolved fluorescence imaging recording of the real time motion of single DNA molecules at the liquid/solid interface. They found that the residence time and the number of immobilized DNA molecules were higher when larger was the pore size and also that the pore diameter must be significantly larger than the DNA short radius in order to allow the DNA capture. These achievements opened new perspectives in the field of conventional liquid chromatography as well as in the size exclusion chromatography and membrane separations.

Kim *et al.*²²⁰ also patterned a nanoporous Al₂O₃ membranes for the extraction of DNA from multiple samples simultaneously using multiple wells. They successfully observed DNA, labeled with a fluorescent marker, collected on the membrane, opening very interesting perspectives for further application in lab- on-a-chip type systems that include DNA extraction steps.

Outstanding is the work reported by Meller's group²²¹, using arrays of nanochannels generated in this case in SiN membranes by electron beam lithography for the optical single-molecule DNA sequencing, employing a novel and ingenious multicolour readout. They first converted target DNA according to a binary code: each nucleotide of the target DNA sequence was bulk biochemically converted to a known oligonucleotide. After that they performed the hybridization with molecular beacons (with two types of fluorophores) and finally optically detected the target DNA by threading of the DNA/beacon complex through the nanochannel. Furthermore, they used the array of nanochannels to sequentially strip-off the beacons and thanks to the specific location of each pore in the visual field of the optical detector, they achieved the simultaneous readout of the array (Figure 12).

Finally, intrinsic photoluminescence properties of nanoporous Al₂O₃ membranes have very recently explored by Marsal's group,²²² and the characteristic barcode signals obtained could open the way for future applications in "smart" biosensors.

Interferometric detection

Porous thin films have also the ability of increasing the sensitivity of interferometric sensors.²²³ The principle of a porous thin film interferometer consists in the measurement of a change in the average index of refraction (η) of a fixed thickness layer (L). Analyte binding in the inner walls of the nanochannel gives rise to a change in the refractive index throughout the film and therefore to a change in the value of ηL .²²⁴ Approaching this property, it deserves to be highlighted the label-free interferometric immunosensor on porous alumina membranes recently reported by Álvarez *et al.*²²⁵ They immobilized antibodies inside the walls of the channels of an Al₂O₃ membrane through protein A binding and detected the specific immunoreaction with IgG by measuring the changes in the interferometric response (Figure 13). However, inherent limitations of this technique such as non-

linearity in the output signal of the sensor, difficulty in distinction of strain direction, and the requirement of complex fringe counting techniques have minimized their use for biosensing on nanoporous materials.

Photonic detection on porous silicon

The science of photonics includes the generation, emission, transmission, modulation, signal processing, switching, amplification, detection and sensing of light using photons (both particle and light nature), covering all technical applications of light over the whole spectrum from ultraviolet over the visible to the near-, mid- and far-infrared. However, in spite of this wide potential, most of the reported applications are in the range of the visible and near infrared light.

Porous silicon (PSi) is an attractive porous material for biological and other applications due to the easy manipulation of their pore size, surface chemistry and optical properties. For example, by tuning the current density, waveform and solution composition used during the electrochemical etch, parameters such as the position, width and intensity of spectral reflectivity peaks can be controlled. This allows the preparation of multilayered PSi (so-called PSi photonic crystals) which can display any number of colors within the visible spectrum, so PSi polytype quasiregular structures with many interesting properties can be easily obtained.

In recent years, PSi photonic crystals have been used as biosensor platforms.^{130,226-229} These multilayered PSi-based biosensors offer many of the advantages both of PSi materials and photonic crystal sensors: large surface area, easy preparation, label-free possibilities and compatibility with standard microelectronics processing. It deserves to be highlighted the work reported by DeLouise's group²³¹ where the label-free detection of a broad range of opiates is achieved. They determined the wavelength shift sensitivity by tracking the infiltration of liquids with known refractive index (η) values and measured the reflectance spectra normal to the surface using a spectrophotometer after exposing the PSi sensor to a normal incident beam of white light (Figure 14).

However, in spite of these promising results, many external random factors produced from the electrochemical process in the fabrication of PSi photonic crystal have a great influence on the

fabrication of accurate ones, limiting the commercial application of PSi photonic crystal based sensors.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS

Nanochannels are showing to be an interesting platform for biosensing applications. This significant growth of interest in nanoporous materials has started from the platforms used for sensing designs with electrochemical detection, mimicking the processes that occur in natural ion channels and taking advantage of the inherent properties of the electrochemical techniques. Since maintaining a natural environment in an artificial device is a difficult task, the construction of fully and highly functional artificial systems with the ability of mimicking natural systems is demanded. This challenging subject led to the creation of different strategies to obtain artificial structures resembling the characteristics of ion channels commonly encountered in the membranes of living systems. In most cases, polymeric membranes are used as substrate material to generate nanochannels, mainly by the track-etch method.

The typical experimental set-up consists in measuring the changes in the electrical conductance between both sides of the membrane where a single nanochannel is inserted, inspired by the Coulter counter device. In this way, many works reporting DNA detection using both biological and solid-state nanochannels have been published in the last years, as summarized in table 1. In a lower extent, proteins and other analytes have also been electrochemically analysed based on the same fundament. As also evidenced in the table, from the wide range of materials and methods available, single solid-state nanochannels, prepared from silicon nitride/oxide membranes taking advantage of the electron beam lithography and specially of the recent advances in ion beam sculpting, together with those prepared from polymeric membranes by the track-etch method have been shown as the most adequate for this kind of sensing. The main advantages of this kind of single nanochannel based electrochemical sensing can be summarised as follows: i) highly sensitivity, ii) rapid and reversible response (allowing real-time monitoring), iii) wide dynamic range, iv) several analytes can be quantified concurrently by a single sensing element, v) the sensing element need not to be highly

selective, as each analyte produces a characteristic signature, vi) fouling of the sensing element cannot give a false reading, as the signal would not be characteristic of an analyte, vii) potential for nanoscale miniaturization.

Furthermore, in the case of the biological ion channels, the most exciting perspectives are focused on their integration in artificial substrates (hybrid biological/solid-state nanochannels) and the potential ability for DNA sequencing, as recently demonstrated and even commercialized by some companies.

The dream of a multianalyte sensing system with arrays of nanochannels is still far to be accomplished, due to the difficulty to adapt the Coulter counter concept to a multireading system. However, the use of arrays of solid-state nanochannels, has opened the way to different and versatile sensing systems, mainly based on the blockage of electrotransducer surfaces. Here Al_2O_3 nanoporous membranes prepared by anodization of the aluminum metal substrate are the most used materials, due to their advantageous properties and mass production opportunities. These nanoporous membranes have been shown also as excellent platforms for the analysis of real samples of *i.e.* human blood, thanks to their filtering properties, allowing to minimize matrix effects. Furthermore, these nanoporous membranes possess optical properties, which allows the sensitive analysis of a variety of analytes using powerful optical techniques such as interferometry or photonics based ones, in the last case taking advantage of the photonic crystals prepared from porous silicon.

These entire advantages make the nanochannel based biosensing systems a very promising research area that should bring wonderful scientific discoveries, with tremendous potential applications in fields such as diagnostics, safety-security and other industrial applications. Nanochannel based biosensing technologies would take advantages from the recent developments of nanoimprinting technologies (*i.e.* roll to roll printing) that together with other fabrication techniques and emerging nanomaterials may bring new opportunities in terms of robustness, mass production and better tailoring of nanochannel based platforms toward various applications better approaching this advantageous technology to more users interested in protein, DNA and cells sensing.

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VOCABULARY BOX

Coulter Counter. Device used for counting and sizing particles suspended in electrolytes. Typically consists in one or more microchannels that separate two chambers containing electrolyte solutions. As fluid containing microparticles or cells is drawn through each microchannel, each particle causes a brief change to the electrical resistance of the liquid which is detected and related with the identity and concentration of the analyte.

α -hemolysin. Protein from the family of the hemolysins, exotoxins produced by bacteria that cause lysis of red blood cells *in vitro*. Its 3D structure usually consists in heptameric or octomeric pores, depending on the bacteria. This structure is extensively approached for the building of biological ion channels by the insertion of the α -hemolysin into artificial membranes, mainly lipid bilayers.

Solid-state ion channels. Nanochannels used as alternative to solve the problems of fragility of the biological ones, consisting in artificial nanochannels embedded in chemically and mechanically robust synthetic membrane.

Stochastic sensing. Sensing method derived from the Coulter counter concept. It consists in the use of a single nanochannel based platform, based on a synthetic or biological membrane as resistive-pulse sensor for the detection of molecular and macromolecule analytes. It entails mounting the membrane containing the nanochannel between two electrolyte solutions, applying a transmembrane potential difference, and measuring the resulting ion current flowing through the electrolyte-filled nanochannel.

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Table 1. Summary of the various nanopores/nanochannels used for biosensing applications.

Nanopore/nanochannel	Single/array	Material/fabrication	Detection	Analyte	Reference	
Biological ion-channel	Single	α -hemolysin pore	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	DNA	51-55	
				Proteins	50, 57-59	
				Enzymes	60,61	
				Peptides	62-64	
				Other analytes	49,65	
	DNA (sequencing perspectives)	21,66-68,71				
Array	α -hemolysin pore	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	DNA	74		
Solid-state nanochannel	Single	SiN-SiO ₂ membranes/ EBL*-FIB*	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	DNA	185-189,191,192	
		Al ₂ O ₃ membranes/EBL-FIB	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	Proteins	197,198	
		Polymeric membranes/ETCH	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	DNA	79,190	
		Glass nanopore electrode	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	Proteins	183, 199-203	
				Other analytes	204,205	
	Array	Al ₂ O ₃ membranes/Anodization	Electrical/Stochastic sensing	Ions	206-208	
	Array	SiN membranes/EBL*	Porous Silicon/Anodization	Electrical/Electrodes blockage	DNA	209-212
				Optical/Fluorescent labels	Proteins	214-216
				Interferometric	DNA	218-220
				Optical/Fluorescent labels	Proteins	225
Photonic-Interferometric				DNA	221	
			Proteins	130,226,228		
			Other analytes	227,229,230		

*EBL:Electron Beam Lithography; FIB: Focused Ion beam; ETCH: Track-etch Method

Figure 1. Biological ion channels. (A) Scheme of a nanochannel sensor based on the concept of the Coulter counter. Adapted from ref 11 with permission. (B). Structure of the main protein ion channels applied in sensing. Adapted from ref 21 with permission. (C) Detailed structure of the heptameric α -hemolysin channel. The cross-sectional view on the right displays the inner cavity (green), inner constriction (red), and β -barrel (blue). Adapted from ref 25 with permission.

Figure 2. Stochastic sensing. (A) Schematic representation of the sensing using an engineered α -hemolysin protein nanochannels inserted in a lipid bilayer membrane. The different conductance between the two sides of the membrane in absence (left) and presence (right) of an analyte in the sample allows its detection and quantification. Adapted from ref 48 with permission. (B) α -hemolysin pore as potential tool for DNA sequencing. The DNA strand enters through the pore (above) and each of the four different bases of DNA could produce characteristic time series recordings (below). Adapted from ref 21 with permission. (C) Third generation DNA sequencing systems developed by: (a) Pacific Biosciences SMRT, using DNA polymerase and differentially labeled nucleotides, (b) Life Technologies Corp., using base fluorescent labeling technology, (c) Oxford Nanopore Technologies[®], using an exonuclease coupled to a modified α -hemolysin nanopore (purple, pictured in cross section) positioned within a lipid bilayer, (d) Ion Torrent[™] sequencing platform, using an ion-sensitive layer and an ion sensor. Adapted from ref 73 with permission.

Figure 3. α -hemolysin nanopore array. (A) Schematic diagram of the system that enables detection of multichannel signals from translocations of single molecules at the α HL nanochannels. Ionic current through a nanochannel is significantly reduced with the translocation of a single linear polymer such as ssDNA/RNA. (a, α -hemolysin nanopore; a', α -hemolysin nanopore blocked by a translocating molecule; b, bilayer lipid membrane; c, micrometer-sized aperture; d, analyte polymer). (B) Experimental setup of multichannel recording. (C) Cross-sectional image of the device. Adapted from ref 74 with permission.

Figure 4. Preparation of solid-state nanochannels for sensing applications using the track-etch method (A-B) and metallic substrates anodization (C). (A) Scheme of a conical nanochannel generation and the corresponding SEM image. (B) Scheme of a gold conical nanochannel formation and the corresponding SEM image. Adapted from ref 91 with permission. (C) (left) Schematic of anodized aluminium oxide (AAO) template formation on ITO glass. Shown are (a) schematic of the set-up system and (b) process of acidic dissolution of the native aluminium oxide as well as (c) the formed layer after the anodization process. (Right) SEM image of the obtained pores. Adapted from ref 103 with permission.

Figure 5. Fabrication of nanoporous films using block copolymers and nanosphere lithography. (A) Schematics for the formation of well-oriented cylinders with perpendicular morphology for PS-PDMS thin films and the corresponding FE-SEM image. Adapted from ref 119 with permission. (B). Schematic diagrams and corresponding SEM images of the nanochannels formation by nanosphere lithography on aluminum substrates: a) surface modification of an aluminum substrate with a close-packed polystyrene sphere monolayer; b) loose-packed polystyrene sphere monolayer *via* the treatment of the O₂ reactive ion etching to increase the distance between each other; c) loose-packed polystyrene sphere monolayer with a layer of aluminum through vacuum evaporation deposition method. d) pre-patterned aluminum substrate with a hexagonal nanoindentation array after polystyrene spheres are removed by ultrasonic treatment. The scale bars are 1 μm. Adapted from ref 124 with permission.

Figure 6. Characterization of porous anodic alumina using imaging techniques. (a) AFM image, (b) AFM three dimensional structure and (c) line profile analysis. (d) FESEM top view, (e) FESEM cross-sectional view and (f) FESEM image of scratched membranes showing three different regions. (g) TEM of a single hexagonal cell and (h) top view of a membrane containing nanopores with diameters of 15 nm. Adapted from ref 139 with permission.

Figure 7. Nanochannels characterization using cyclic voltammetry. (A) Scheme of the electrochemical cell set-up for track-etch polycarbonate membrane on a gold film electrode. (B) Scheme of the diffusional flux of molecules to the electrode at fast (a), low (b) and very low scan rates. (C) Cyclic voltammograms obtained in 1.0 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ / 0.1 M KNO_3 at 5 different scan rates (a) and the same for blocked nanochannels (b). Adapted from ref 153 with permission.

Figure 8. Nanochannels characterization using RMN and X-ray diffraction. (A) Continuous-flow ^{129}Xe NMR spectra of a porous Al-based coordination polymer at variable temperatures (a); Crystal structure of the same polymer, viewed along the channel axis (b); Xenon atoms can diffuse in the large channels but cannot enter in the small channels (c). Colors are as follows: carbon, light blue; oxygen, red; aluminum, blue; xenon, yellow. Adapted from ref 163 with permission. (B) X-ray diffraction measurements of free-standing 20 nm thick $\text{In}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{As}$ nanomembrane. Adapted from ref 165 with permission.

Figure 9. Protein sensing using chemically modified single solid-state nanochannels. (A) (a) Cross-sectional sketch depicting the principle of single-molecule sensing with a nanochannel: a membrane with a single nanochannel separates two electrolyte-filled compartments. Charged analyte molecules (red) are electrokinetically driven through the channel and are detected by transient blockades in the trans-channel ion current. When the channel is equipped with a specific receptor site (green), the blockade time reflects the binding time of the analyte (ligand) to the receptor; (b) Schematic cross-section of a gold-coated SiN nanochannel functionalized with thiols and NTA receptor thiols. The Ni₂p (green) loaded nitrilotriacetic receptor (black) specifically binds His₆-tagged proteins (red); (c) Representative current *versus* time trace signals. Adapted from ref 196 with permission. (B) Schematic representation of a single conical nanochannel with covalently immobilized terpyridine ligand for lactoferrin detection, *via* the metal ion affinity-based biomolecular recognition, and graphs of the current vs voltage characteristics of a single conical nanochannel with before (left) and after (right) the covalent attachment of terpyridine, followed by the addition of various concentration of lactoferrin. Adapted from ref 202 with permission.

Figure 10. Other analytes sensing with solid-state nanochannels. (A) Biomimetic potassium responsive nanochannel: (a) G4 DNA is immobilized onto the inner surface of a single nanochannel. In absence of K^+ the G4 DNA relaxes to a loosely packed single-stranded structure. (b) In presence of K^+ the G4 DNA folds into densely packed rigid quadruplex structures that partially decrease the effective nanochannel diameter. (c) After adding complementary DNA strands, G4 DNA forms a closely packed arrangement of double-stranded DNA on the single nanochannel. Adapted from ref 204 with permission. (B) Characterization of nanoparticles surface charge: Pressure in the top fluid cell is controlled *via* a flexible tubing connection by varying the height difference between the water level in a partially submerged buret and the water level of a large water reservoir. The buret is equilibrated with atmospheric pressure by opening a valve. The graph represent S-curves obtained for various polystyrene particles, acquired using the variable pressure method. Adapted from ref 205 with permission.

Figure 11. Protein sensing technology using an anodized aluminium oxide (AAO) nanoporous membrane array and AuNPs labels. (A) The matrix interferents in the blood sample (cells or other material) remain outside the channels and the proteins enter inside and are recognized by specific antibodies (left) generating a blockage in the diffusion of electroactive species (Fe^{2+}) that can be enhanced using AuNPs labels in a sandwich assay (right). (B) Electrochemical cell set-up. (C) Top view of an AAO membrane on which a drop of blood (50 μL) was deposited. (D) Cross-sectional view of the same membrane after an immunoreaction using AuNPs labels and silver enhancement (white silver crystals are observed). Adapted from ref 214 and ref 215 with permission.

Figure 12. Simultaneous multiple optical DNA sequencing. (A) Bulk biochemical conversion of each nucleotide of the target DNA sequence to a known oligonucleotide, followed by hybridization with molecular beacons. Threading of the DNA/beacon complex through a nanochannel allows optical detection of the target DNA sequence. (B) Schematic illustration of the conceptual parallel readout scheme. Adapted from ref 221 with permission.

Figure 13. Label-free interferometric immunosensor. (A) Sensing principle: White light reflection from the porous aluminum oxide films generates a thin film interference spectral pattern that changes as a result of the modification in refractive index of the film generated by the immunoreaction. (B) Experiments demonstrating specific binding affinity and controls for the interferometric immunosensor. Adapted from ref 225 with permission.

Figure 14. Photonic sensor on porous silicon (PSi). (A) Cross-sectional SEM of PSi Bragg mirror architecture. Inset depicts schematic of opiate-analogue functionalized PSi. (B) In the absence of free drug in urine, maximum the Ab binds to surface-attached opiate analogue resulting in (C) a maximum wavelength shift response. (D) Opiates in urine compete with surface attached opiate-analogue for Ab binding sites, resulting in a proportional decrease in the wavelength shift response (E). Adapted from ref 230 with permission.

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